

A Method of Multivariate Modelling using Single-Variable Regression

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Abstract

Multivariate data regression is often restricted to sets of data with smooth relations for the sake of accuracy. This paper proposes an alternative method that aids to eliminate this restriction at the cost of elegance and ease of differentiating. This method requires no computationally difficult calculations above simple single variable regression methods.

1 Introduction

This method progresses through variables in steps.

In general, the method requires two 'base' variables and a variable that is being modelled. Any other variables are left on hold. The order in which variables are modelled is not important.

As a requirement, S 'base' functions relating the base variables within the range of the modelling variable have to be known. A constant interval T between base functions is assumed.

For example:

Select x , y as base variables, and z as the variable to be modelled.

If $f_z(x)$ represents the y value as a function of x for a certain value of z , required are:

$f_{z_{min}}(x)$
 $f_{z_{min}+T}(x)$
 $f_{z_{min}+2T}(x)$
..
 $f_{z_{max}}(x)$

Note that

$$z_{max} = z_{min} + ST$$

These functions can be obtained using simple regression methods, such as single-variable polynomial regression.

The method operates by summing these functions individually, each multiplied by a 'relevance function'. The purpose of these relevance functions is to increase and decrease the weight of each function according to the value of the modelling variable.

(1) Is a simple example of a relevance function, again using z as the modelling variable. Its graph is shown in figure 1. Note that z_b is the value of z for which the base function on which the relevance function is applied is valid.

$$r_{z_b}(z) = \frac{1}{(z - z_b)^2 + 1} \tag{1}$$

This a sub optimal relevance function, but it is used in the introduction for simplicity. Variations are discussed in section 2.

In general, then:

$$g(x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}) = \sum_{i=0}^S r_{((x_{n+1})_{min+iT})(x_{n+1})} f_{((x_{n+1})_{min+iT})(x, \dots, x_n)} \quad (2)$$

Which in turn could be used as a base function for a next variable, etc.
There is no theoretical limit to the amount of variables for which this method is available.

2 Variations of the relevance function

Define once again base variables as x and y and modelling variable as z.

Define $P = \frac{z-z_b}{T}$.

In general, as long as function $r_{z_b}(z)$ equals around unity at z_b and falls off to around zero at $z_b + 1$ and $z_b - 1$, it can be used as a relevance function. However, there are certain qualities that should be sought after:

- In a sequence, the sum of all functions should hover as closely to unity as possible within the range of z.
- (unless otherwise desired) individual functions should drop off somewhat linearly around z_b , to ensure smooth transitions between base functions.

A near perfectly linear variation is the one presented:

$$r_{z_b}(z) = \frac{P + 1}{(2P + 1)^n + 1} + \frac{1 - P}{(2P - 1)^n + 1}$$

With n being a constant with value $n \geq 30$.

Experimentally, another solution was found as presented:

$$r_{z_b}(z) = \frac{0.3211}{\sum_{i=1}^6 P^{2i} - 0.9P^4 + 0.38}$$

This function initially has a slow drop-off causing the final function to be more closely related to the base functions. Also, due to the weaker drop-off, values are influenced more actively by surrounding base functions. Any base function defines a value by at most 80%, whereas this value is 100% in the first variation. Therefore this function could be chosen in situations where this quality is desirable.

3 Advantage

There are several advantages to this method, the most important one of which is the fact that very steep / changeable relations can accurately be modelled. The only requirement in this aspect is that there are at least two variables with a smooth relation to select as base variables. If this is not the case, an method to find a solution is presented in Appendix A.

Other advantages include the ease of computation, as a simple single-variable regression algorithm together with one to apply this method are enough to produce results.

Finally, the possibility of extensive variation of the relevance function even between individual base functions gives the user a lot of freedom in generating the function.

The main disadvantage of this method is that it the resultant function is significantly harder to differentiate or integrate than if it had been generated using traditional methods.

4 Figures

Figure 1: Simple relevance function for $T = 1$ and $z_b = 0$

A Appendix

If no smooth relation between two variables can be found, it might help to part the range into smooth sections. These sections can then be fitted and combined to a single function using one of the following equations:

1. $h_1(x) = 0.5 \frac{|s|}{s} + 0.5$

2. $h_2(x) = \frac{1}{s^n + 1}$

With n is a constant with value $n \geq 30$.

These equations aim to approximate either zero or one dependant upon the constraint s . For equation 1, $h_1(x) = 1$ for $s > 0$ and otherwise (except when $s = 0$) $h_1(x) = 0$. For example, function $l(x) = xh_1(x)$ with $s = x - 1$, $l(x) = 0$ for $x < 1$ and $l(x) = x$ for $x > 1$.

For equation 2, the constraint is in the form

$$s = \frac{x - x_{cent}}{radius}$$

where x_{cent} is the location of the center of the section for which $f(x) = 1$, and radius is the distance around it.

Be aware that equation 1 contains a perforation at $s = 0$.